

Al-Bay Bithaman Ajil (BBA) as Practiced in Malaysia: A Critical Review

By
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ABSTRACT

Islamic financial industry experienced an extraordinary growth over the last few decades and promises to grow even further. The current global financial crisis made some believe that the time has come for the Islamic finance to assume a greater role in the world's financial architecture. They failed to realize that the Islamic finance has several issues that need to be addressed in order to avoid its alienation from the ideals as advocated by the pioneers of the Islamic finance. One of these issues is the *al-bay bithaman ajil*, or better known by its acronyms BBA. BBA initially was developed as a temporary solution for Islamic banks in Malaysia. However, its status has not been changed yet as it is predominantly used by the Islamic banks in Malaysia. This paper tries to critically review the BBA and its practice within Malaysia. It argues that the current practice of BBA is nothing more but a legal device. If this practice continues, the paper argues, it will lead to the convergence of Islamic banks towards its conventional counterparts. Finally, it is believed that the way out of this situation is either to use BBA mechanism in its true sense or to develop new modes of finance that will be a better representative of the Islamic financial system.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance is at the crossroad. On one side the global economic crisis provides a golden opportunity for the Islamic finance industry to establish itself better and prosper due to its conservatism towards speculation (*maysir*) and interest (*ribā*). However, on the other side, the Islamic finance industry is also faced with

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numerous challenges, one of them being a continuous debate on the validity of *al-bay bithaman ājil*, or better known by its acronyms BBA. BBA refers to a credit sale or a sale with delayed payment. It is a type of sale that is the most widely used by Islamic banks in Malaysia. BBA is also known as *bay muajjal* and *murābahah* in Pakistan and the Middle Eastern countries.

Last year the High Court of Malaysia ruled out that ten Bank Islam Malaysia (Bank Islam) contracts were structurally faulty and that defaulters did not have to pay more than the original financing amount, thus depriving Bank Islam of the *profit* arising from the transaction.

Following the appeal filed by Bank Islam, the Court of Appeal held that the BBA facility offered by Islamic financial institutions is valid and legally binding. This decision was unanimously made by judges of the Court of Appeal, namely Datuk Md Raus Sharif, Datuk Abdul Hamid Embong and Datuk Ahmad Maarop, on 31 March, 2009. The said decision reaffirmed that Bank Islam's practices in relation to BBA contracts are *Shariah*-compliant and valid. The Court of Appeal also reiterated that a BBA contract is a sale transaction and therefore, it must not be compared to a loan transaction.

The unanimous decision of the Court of Appeal would mean a certain relief to local Islamic banks that had earlier feared a potential avalanche in defaults of Islamic contracts, especially for home financing. Although the Court of Appeal approved the practice of BBA, this practice is still overshadowed with a lot of issues, the most important being its application of *bay'inah* (buy-back) contract.² Raising issues about current practices within the Islamic finance industry should be welcomed and addressed with the true intention of improving them.

The time is ripe for Islamic finance to step forward and find its way out of the chains of the conventional finance domain. An attempt should be made by both practitioners and scholars to come up with genuine products that are free from controversies and based on Islamic principles stipulated within Islamic law, *Sharī'ah*.

Current issues and problems with BBA arise from its similarity to conventional practices explicitly based on *ribā*. Many scholars as well as sincere practitioners see it as ruses (*hilah*) to provide legal justification for interest. To continue replicating conventional products and practices will lead to the convergence

² “*Bay al-inah* is generally known as sale based on the transaction of *Nasi'ah* (delay). The (prospective) debtor sells to the (prospective) creditor some object for cash which is payable immediately; the debtor immediately buys simultaneously the same object for a greater amount for a future date. Thus the transaction amounts to a loan. The difference between the two prices represent the interest. Such contract was evolved in the early period of Islam and it exists for the fundamental reason that a loan for interest is forbidden because it is equivalent to usury (*riba*). In this contract, there is an economic interest for both the borrower and the lender, which at the same time circumvents the prohibition of usury.” (Rosly & Sanusi, 1999, September)

of Islamic finance with the conventional sector. If this is the case then Islamic finance is doomed to fail, as it will be following in the footsteps of its stepmother, interest-based financing.

This paper will try to review and analyze the BBA mode of finance as it is being implemented in Malaysia. This paper consists of six sections including the introduction. Second section deals with general overview of BBA, its definition, determination of price and *Shariah* rulings with regard to it. Section three focuses on the overdependence of Islamic banks on BBA mode of financing while section four consists of detailed explanation of its mechanism. In section five, an attempt is made to briefly summarize the objections related to and vulnerability of the BBA and its application. Finally, section six is left for concluding remarks and recommendations.

2.0 GENERAL OVERVIEW OF BBA

2.1 Definition

Al-Bay Bithaman Ājil (BBA) originates from a contract called *murābahah*. Therefore, it is important for us to first define *murābahah* as a contract. *Murābahah* simply means an increase or growth from the Arabic verb *rabaha* or *rabiha* (رَبَّحَ) which also may imply profit.³ In other words, *murābahah* is a 'cost-plus financing' (Thani, Mohamed, & Hassan, 2003, p. 57), 'mark-up sale' (Rosly, 2005, p. 87) or resale based on profit margin above the cost.

Literal meaning of *al-bay bithaman ājil* is as follows: *al-bay* (البيع) means a sale, *thaman* (ثمن) means price, *ājil* (أجل) means deferment. BBA is a sale and not a loan, but this is the sale with deferred payment (Chapra, 1985, p. 169; Rosly, 2005, p. 88). "It is an extension of the *murābahah* (cost plus) contract, whereby the commodity exchanged is 'delivered' immediately but the sale price (with profit) is paid in instalments, over a long period (the *murābahah* itself being generally for short periods)" (Meera & Dzuljastri, 2005, p. 7). Muhammad Taqi Usmani defines it as, "[a] sale in which the parties agree that the payment of price shall be deferred..." (Usmani, 2002, p. 40).

In this regard, BBA contract is a sub-contract of *murābahah* whereby the settlement of the price is made based on instalments. Under this contract, the delivery of the goods is taking place on the spot while the price, cost plus a profit margin, is paid in instalments (Meera & Dzuljastri, 2005). Originally, *murābahah* as well as BBA are two particular types of sale and not modes of financing (Usmani, 2002, p. 37 & 41).

2.2 Determination of the Price

The price of the BBA can be calculated either through lump-sum or percentage profit margins. Ibn Mas'ūd (r.a.) made a ruling that it is allowed to declare lump-sum or percentage profit margins (El-Gamal, 2000, p. 10). Furthermore, all schools of

³ The verb رَبَّحَ or رَبَّحَ (*rabaha* or *rabiha*) means to gain, profit, to win while رَبَّحَ (ribh) pl. أَرْبَاحَ (*arbāh*) means gain, profit, benefit, interest; pl. proceeds, returns, revenues, dividends, etc. See: (Wehr, 1980, p. 321).

fiqh, Hanafī, Mālikī, Shāfiī and Hanbalī, allowed that the profit margin, in case of *murābahah*, can be expressed either in lump-sum or in percentage (Abu-Ghuddah, 2003, pp. 26-27; Usmani, 2002, p. 41).

Nothing in Islamic law dictates how the price for such a sale is determined; it is simply whatever the parties agree upon. Therefore, nothing prevents the seller from linking the sale price to the period of time for which credit is extended, and Islamic institutions in fact do so, employing formulae using LIBOR and other economic indicators. In their actual documentation, however, banks usually avoid mentioning any such procedure for fixing the price, since it is easily mistaken for a charge of interest. (Vogel & Hayes, 1998, p. 139)

Many people object to its price determination and its linkage to the interest rate charged by conventional banks. Usmani (2002) believes that as cash *murābahah* can be priced over the cost by any amount, in a similar way the credit *murābahah* can be charged higher. According to all the four schools of *fiqh* and the majority of the Muslim jurists, it is allowed for a seller to set the price of a credit sale higher than the price for a cash sale. However, it is not allowed to set many prices, for example to set two or three or even more prices for one transaction, since it will lead to uncertainty, which makes the contract void.

Having said this, it is obvious from the above discussion that there is no legal constraints to use whatever benchmark available. Consequently, using LIBOR as a benchmark does not render a sale contract invalid or *harām*. Nevertheless, any reference to interest (in this case LIBOR, KLIBOR, etc.) should be avoided as much as possible.

2.4 *Sharah* Rulings on BBA

Even though, the Middle Eastern *ulama* do not accept and practice BBA as a mode of financing still it is approved by the majority of Muslim scholars. Although the BBA mechanism is a *Shariah*-compliant, still we can find some implementations of BBA and *murābahah* which are "with or without "full" *Shariah* compliance" – says Obiyathullah (2005, p. 68).

In principle, the BBA is allowed by *Shariah* (Abu-Ghuddah, 2003, p. 17). Its permissibility is found in *Al-Qur'an*, *Sunnah* and *Ijma*. Those who support BBA contract refer to the verse in *sūrah al-Baqarah* where Allah (swt) says: "...Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury" (Al-Baqarah, 2:275). Ahmad, Abu Dāwūd and al-Dāraquṭnī narrated *hadīth* where the Prophet (pbuh) entrusted Abdullah ibn Umar (r.a.) with responsibility of preparing the army for a military expedition (cited in Abu-Ghuddah, 2003, p. 22). Accordingly, 'Abdullah bought mounts by offering to pay almost double the price for a single mount.

According to the *Mejelle*, the *instalment* sale is good (Rahman, 1967, pp. 35-36). It is believed that the *Shariah* allows this type of trade, since there is need for it by people (Abu-Ghuddah, 2003, p. 18). Everything is permissible, in principle, unless otherwise stated in sources of *Shariah* (i.e. the *Qur'an*, *Sunnah*, *Ijma'* and *Qiyas*). This is based on well known legal maxim, which states that everything, every contract is permissible or in Arabic: الأصل في الأشياء الإباحة

The Council of the Islamic *Fiqh* Academy, during its sixth and seventh session held in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia agreed on the permissibility of instalment sale (i.e. *Al-Bay Al-Mu'ajjal*). It says that it is allowed to have different prices for cash and instalment sale. However, once the contract is signed there should be only one price, whether the cash or instalment price (Islamic Fiqh Academy, 2000, p. 103 & 135).⁴ There are few scholars who disagree with the permissibility of BBA. Some of them are Zaynul Ābidīn Ali bin al-Husain, Imam Yahya, Ustaz Abdul Rahman Abdul Khaliq and Ustaz Nizam al-Dīn °Abdul Hamīd (Abu-Ghuddah, 2003, p. 21).

Shaykh Ahmad Kutty, Dr. Yusuf Al-Qaradawi and Dr. Monzer Kahf,⁵ among other contemporary scholars, allowed the instalment sale. In their views, it is a necessity for the people and without allowing the instalment sale it would put the hardship on them in performing their everyday life activities, and that is contrary to the Qur'anic verse stating "... Allah intends every facility for you He does not want to put you to difficulties..." (Al-Qur'an, al-Baqarah: 185). Furthermore, the Holy Qur'an says: "And strive in His cause as ye ought to strive (with sincerity and under discipline): He has chosen you and has imposed no difficulties on you in religion..." (Al-Qur'an, al-Hajj: 78). The Council of Islamic Ideology of Pakistan accepted BBA as a financial instrument, but with some reservations (Ahmad, 1993).

3.0 OVERDEPENDENCE OF ISLAMIC BANKS ON BBA FINANÇING

Many authors are worried about the Islamic banks. The reason for this concern lies in overdependency of Islamic banks on debt-based financing. "...Islamic banking has come under increasing criticism, from its own ranks and from the public, for its heavy reliance on synthetic *murābahah*" (Vogel & Hayes, 1998, p. 143). The minimum and maximum proportions in Islamic banks occupied by BBA and its variants are 45% and 93% (Anwar, 2006, p. 356).

Why do Islamic banks mainly rely on these two trading modes, *murābahah* and *al-bay bithaman ājil*? Several scholars gave their reasons and opinions trying to answer this question. We will try to mention some of these answers in the following. According to Muhammad Anwar, there are two explanations for that (Anwar, 2006, p. 359). Firstly, they are complying with the commands of the Holy *Qur'an* in verses already stated above (2:275 and 4:29). Secondly, it is easy for Islamic banks to, "charge time value of money in the name of a profit margin on their financing in place of the interest charged by the conventional banks." Furthermore, Islamic banks are nothing more than small islands in the sea of *ribā*-based banking. This is also one of the reasons why Islamic banks heavily rely on fixed return facilities such as *murābahah*, BBA and the like (Ali, 1992, p. 351).

Vogel and Hayes mention some characteristics of *murābahah* which made it the most popular mode of finance of Islamic banks. *Murābahah* - according to them - can be used for short-term as well as intermediate-term financing (Vogel & Hayes,

⁴ Resolution No. (51/2/6) of Sixth Session and Resolution No. (64/2/7) of Seventh Session held between 14-20 March, 1990 and 9-14 May, 1992 respectively.

⁵ Their *fatwas* on the issue of instalment sale can be found at <<http://www.islamonline.net>>.

1998, p. 212 & 240). Through *murābahah* financing Islamic banks create an unconditional debt in a fixed amount that can be easily collateralized or secured. Furthermore, there is no need to monitor the client's business and honesty as is the case with *mushārahah*. Meanwhile, it mimics conventional interest-based lending, being highly liquid and bearing minimum risks (Vogel & Hayes, 1998, p. 240).

Table 1: Modes of Islamic Finance in Malaysia (% share of total)

Modes of Finance	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005
<i>Al-Bay Bithaman Ajil</i>	48.3	49.1	47.7	49.9	40.7
<i>Al-Ijārah</i>	4.3	3	1.4	24	31.6
<i>Al-Ijārah Thumma Al-Bay</i>	22.2	23.3	27.6	-	-
<i>Al-Istisna'</i>	0.9	1.3	0.6	1.2	0.9
<i>Mudharaba & Mushāraka</i>	1.4	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.3
<i>Murābahah</i>	7	7.3	6.2	7	6.9
Other Islamic Contracts	15.9	15.3	16	17.4	19.6
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Bank Negara Annual Report (various issues)

This extravagant usage of fixed-rate-short-term type of financial instruments by Islamic banks is seen by some as "...'deviation' from the Islamic ideal..." (Naqvi, 2000, p. 41) – i.e. profit and loss sharing (PLS) instruments. Furthermore, this excessive reliance of Islamic banks on fixed return modes may result in loss of their comparative advantage in the long-run. It is for these reasons that scholars have been warning us about this malady of Islamic banks, saying that Islamic banks will, "lose ground against conventional banks as they are also offering products with similar, if not the same, characteristics. In order to gain competitive advantage and product differentiation, Islamic banks had better evolve mechanisms for successful application of variable returns modes" (Noman, 2002). The above mentioned practice of Islamic banks will lead them to assimilation with conventional banks. In other words, if Islamic banks continue current practices it will lead to the convergence of Islamic banks into conventional ones.

Until and unless Islamic banks and financial institutions change this approach, they will remain in the shadows of the conventional financial system. In this regard Muhammad Anwar (2006, p. 357) says:

Proper application of the Islamic modes would have set Islamic Banks apart from the conventional banks, but this did not happen in reality because the Islamic banks manipulated the trading modes in ways that retained their identity as lenders rather than traders and entrepreneurs. Therefore, there ought to be some measures to ensure that Islamic banks are transformed from the traditional lenders to the Islamic entrepreneurs. Otherwise, the question regarding the Islamicity of their operation... would continue to confuse the Muslim mind.

Although BBA financing is permissible according to *Shariah*, many Muslim scholars have warned us not to use it extensively, due to its similarity to the

conventional interest-based transactions. Using BBA "widely and indiscriminately...might open a back door to "interest"" (Qureshi, 1990, p. 52). It is worth mentioning here M. Umer Chapra's view on the issue. Addressing the issue of *murābahah* and BBA he says:

This is a perfectly legitimate transaction according to the *Shari'ah*, provided that the risk for the transaction is borne by the financier until the possession has been passed to the customer. For such a transaction to be legal, the bank would have to sign two separate contracts, one with the supplier and the other with the customer. It would not be lawful for the bank to have only one contract with the purchaser, the only service rendered by it being the remittance of the amount to the supplier on behalf of the purchaser. In this case the transaction would not be different from an interest-based arrangement. In addition to the dual contract, the bank would have to continue to be responsible until the goods were actually delivered to the customer, not necessarily by the bank, according with specifications and other terms of the contract. (Chapra, 1985, p. 170)

From the above statement, it is obvious how the *murābahah* and BBA transactions should be carried out in reality. He further goes on by concluding that, "the danger will, however, always remain that the *mu'ajjal* and *murābahah* forms of sales may deteriorate into purely financing arrangements with the agreed profit margin being no more than a camouflage for interest" (Chapra, 1985, p. 170).

4.0 HOW DOES IT WORK? – MODUS OPERANDI OF BBA

Since *ribā* is prohibited by the Holy *Qur'an*, Islamic banks in Malaysia have introduced *al-bay bithaman ājil* (BBA) to cater for the needs of Muslim clients. Islamic banks are not supposed to provide ordinary offering loans. Instead Islamic bank "...*theoretically* purchases the house from the developer at market price (i.e. cost price) and sells it to the customer at a mark-up price" (Rosly, 2005, p. 122).⁶ However, as the citation says, this is done only "*theoretically*" while it is, in fact, one using buy-back (*bay al-inah*) transaction.

Specifically, BBA financing is implemented in the following way. Mr. Ahmad, as is the case in conventional banking, will pay a down payment (let us say RM40,000 or 20 percent assuming that the price is RM200,000) and sign sales and purchase (S&P) agreement. Now, the bank, in order to secure the ownership (*milkiyyah*), will purchase that asset from Mr. Ahmad through the Property Purchase Agreement (PPA). In fact, this purchase takes place only on the papers, since there is no real transfer of the ownership as there is no evidence of registration and stamp duty. Now, note that the bank will purchase that asset from Mr. Ahmad for the remaining amount of money needed to buy the whole house (i.e. RM160,000). Through the introduction of PPA the bank gets the rights over the asset and becomes the legal owner of it. Once the PPA is executed, the bank will sell the asset back to Mr. Ahmad at the deferred price. This deferred price or the selling price would be the cost price plus the profit margin. For calculating profit margin, Islamic banks, without mentioning it, use some interest rate benchmark such as LIBOR. Therefore,

⁶ Here, the *italics* is ours for emphasis.

the annual profit rate (APR) of Islamic banks would be very much close (if not the same) to the annual interest rate of conventional banks. If the APR and contracting period are the same as the annual interest rate and period in the case of conventional loan (i.e. 10%), then the monthly instalment will be the same as well, i.e. RM1,544.03⁷ for next 20 years (i.e. 240 instalments assuming that annual interest rate is 10%). This is illustrated in the Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Actual *al-bay' bithaman ājil*

1. Customer pays down payment RM40,000 and signs S&P
2. Bank buys the house through the customer for RM160,000 & immediately sells it back to the customer for price = RM160,000 + profit margin
3. Customer repays the bank through instalments

In brief, BBA sale contract consists of the followings:

- a) Property Purchase Agreement (PPA): Bank purchases the asset from customer.
- b) Property Sale Agreement (PSA): Bank sells the asset to the customer at BBA price, i.e. cost plus the profit margin.
- c) Deeds of Assignment/Charge: The asset is withheld as collateral by the bank (Rosly, 2005, p. 91).
- d)

Figure 2: Real *al-bay' bithaman ājil*

1. Customer identifies an house to be purchased
2. Bank informally purchases the house from the owner on cash basis, eg. RM160,000
3. Bank sells the house to the customer at a selling price= RM160,000 + profit margin
4. Customer pays the bank on instalments

The real BBA financing mechanism is presented in the Figure 2 above. This figure shows how BBA *should be* carried out. Firstly, Mr. Ahmad identifies the property he wishes to buy. Then he approaches the bank and informs it about his

⁷ Computed using the standard formula for present value of annuities, i.e.

$$PV = \frac{Pmt}{i} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right] \text{ which gives } Pmt = \frac{i(1+i)^n PV}{(1+i)^n - 1}$$

intention. Secondly, the bank purchases the property from the developer. Thirdly, the bank sells the property to Mr. Ahmad, who gets delivery of the property on the spot. Finally, Mr. Ahmad repays the deferred price to the bank on the instalment basis throughout the agreed period. Unfortunately, this is not a viable option for an Islamic bank due to the nature of the banking business and legal restrictions which are beyond the scope of this paper.

Now let us see what happens under the conventional banking. Let us assume that a customer, Ahmad, wants to buy a house which costs RM200,000. He would approach the developer and sign a sale and purchase agreement (S&P) and pay, let's say, 20 percent of the whole amount, i.e. RM40,000 as a down payment. Then he would approach a bank, say a bank A, for the financing of the rest. If the bank A approves the loan, Ahmad would get RM160,000 loan and pay a monthly instalment of RM1,544.03 for next 20 years (i.e. 240 instalments assuming that annual interest rate is 10%) to the bank. The very same house will be used as collateral. This will be done through the contract called deeds of assignment/charge. Final amount payable to the bank would be RM370,567.20.⁸ Therefore, the profit to the bank would be RM210,567.20.⁹ In short, under the conventional banking system the financing consists of two contracts: (i) Contract of loan between the bank and Mr. Ahmad; and (ii) Deeds of Assignment/Charge (Rosly, 2005, p. 89).

As mentioned earlier in this paper, the bank uses the PPA and the PSA simultaneously. The aforementioned agreements, PPA and PSA, are only 'legal devices' since the real transfer of ownership is not taking place. In addition to this artificial mechanism, the bank, as a seller, does not hold any liability to the goods sold. As a result, the customer or the buyer cannot claim anything if any defects, shrinkage or faults occur. To see the real effects of the above scenario refer to the Table 2 below:

Table 2: Comparison between conventional loan & BBA

Price of House = RM200,000	Customer RM40,000	Bank RM160,000
	APR = 10% Conventional Loan	APR = 10% BBA
Monthly Payment	RM1544.03	RM1544.03
Total Payment in 20 years	RM370,567.20	RM370,567.20
Total Interest/Profit to Bank	RM210,567.20	RM210,567.20
APR	10%	10%
Balance after 10 years	RM116,838.55	RM185,283.60

The distinguished feature of BBA, when compared with conventional loan, is with regard to the balance of financing before the stipulated date in the contract. For example, if Ahmad wants to settle his debt after 10 years, he would still owe the bank the remaining 120 instalment payments; in this case it is RM185,283.60. This

⁸ Found by $RM1544.03 \times 240 = RM370,567.20$.

⁹ Found by $RM370,567.20 - RM160,000 = RM210,567.20$.

amount represents the interest-cum-profit paid for a loan over the 20-year period under the conventional mortgage plan. It is also clear from this figure that the amount due by Ahmad after 10 years is still higher than the original amount borrowed by him, i.e. RM160,000. It is obvious that Islamic bank creates an extra burden upon the client and has negative socio-economic consequences. It is believed that, following the fractional reserve system, Islamic banks are "very damaging to the economy" (Meera & Dzuljastri, 2005). It is also believed that under this fractional reserve banking system, a customer using Islamic facilities through BBA owes more money to the bank than by using conventional modes of finance, at any point prior to the end of the period. It is for this reason that Islamic banking attracted even conventional banks to provide Islamic financing (Meera & Dzuljastri, 2005).

5.0 SOME ISSUES FACED BY BBA

5.1 Objections Related to the BBA

BBA as a mode of financing has been criticized for quite a long time. Its validity has been questioned throughout literature. Here we will try to summarize some of these objections related to the BBA contract. Some of the objections are:

- i) *Similarity with Interest Rate*: One of the critics related to the BBA contract is that it is very similar to the conventional interest-based financing. It is said that, "the selling price of the BBA facility is similar to nominal value of a loan plus the total interest payment" (Kamel, 1998, p. 122). Some would argue that it is "the closest Islamic analogue to interest finance..." (Vogel & Hayes, 1998, p. 139 & 240). Comparing the characteristics of Islamic or interest-free banks and conventional banks Metwally concluded that, "[i]nterest-free banks rely heavily on the *Murābaha* method of finance which is based on the use of a mark-up which does not differ much from the interest charge" (Metwally, 1997, p. 98). This again proves our previous claim that these practices would lead to the convergence of the Islamic banks into conventional banks.
- ii) As we have already explained above under the sub-topic *Determination of the Price*, we can see that the seller and buyer are at liberty to agree at any price. Therefore, when performing *bay'* (sale), the seller can take into account different factors, including the time of payment. However, this can be done only at the time when the sale is taking place and cannot be extended later in case of default by the buyer (Usmani, 2002, pp. 44-48). However, even though the penalties should not be there in the Islamic banking system, yet Islamic banks do charge penalties for the late payments and defaults.
- iii) *Use of the Interest Rate as a Benchmark*: Islamic banks and financial institutions commonly use LIBOR as a benchmark, or in case of Malaysia KLIBOR, in order to determine their profit margin. Using the interest rate is considered undesirable – according to Usmani – but it does not make the transaction invalid or *harām*, because the contract in itself does not contain interest. However, he thinks that this practice should be replaced with some kind of Islamic benchmark (Usmani, 2002, pp. 48-49). This practice of using the interest rate as a benchmark is yet another proof of the convergence that is taking place and that we are trying to highlight in this paper.

- iv) *The Question of 'Iwad* (عوض - *Countervalue*): This is one of the major objections related to the BBA facilities offered by Islamic banks. It is believed that a valid sale must meet some requirements, namely: there should be no uncertainty (*gharar*) and the equivalent countervalue (*'iwad*) should exist (Rosly, 2001, p. 187).¹⁰ There are three principal components of *'iwad*, namely: risk and liability (*ghurm* and *daman*), work (*'amal*) and capital (*māl*) (Rosly, 2001, p. 187 & 193). This implies that any sale conducted by Islamic bank must contain *'iwad* for the profit to be considered legal. As stated by Rosly, "...*'iwad* is the basic trait or *conditio sine qua non* of a lawful trade" (2001, p. 191). In other words, a profit from a sale which does not contain *'iwad* is not a lawful profit. Islamic banks, in their financing modes, should observe *'iwad* and comprising of those three principal components mentioned above (i.e. *ghurm* and *daman*, *'amal* and *māl*). However, in the case of BBA financing there is "relatively no trace of risk-taking and value addition" (Rosly, 2001, p. 196; Vogel & Hayes, 1998, pp. 139-143 & 240).
- v) *Issue of Default*: In the event of default, under a conventional loan, a defaulter has to pay only the loan amount plus accrued interest and other charges. Moreover, the sum that the borrower has to pay is limited to the period from the release of the loan until full settlement thereof. Besides that, once the property is disposed at market value, there is usually little that the customer has to add. On the contrary, under the BBA scheme, the bank claims the loan amount as well as the profit margin thereon for the full tenure of the facility. Thus, the bank here claims a profit on the unexpired tenure as well. Since the customer is to pay the full amount for the full tenure, he should be allowed to benefit for full tenure as well. Likewise, the profit charged for unearned tenure is against the principles of BBA, and as such it cannot be considered as actual profit and claimed under the BBA (refer back to Figure 2 above).

5.2 Vulnerability of the BBA Contract

As we have already mentioned, BBA, in its true sense, is a sale contract and therefore, profit earned from BBA is *halāl*. The uniqueness of BBA facility lies in its selling price. This price (i.e. the price of goods sold through BBA) is fixed throughout the contract period, and it cannot be changed since the changing of the price would make the contract null and void (Rosly, 2005, p. 122).

In case of conventional banking and finance, interest rate on loans can be adjusted at any time in line with market forces. This means that when the overall interest rate is rising the borrowers will pay higher interest rates monthly and when an interest rate is falling, they will pay lower interest rates on a monthly basis. We see that the loan price is determined by the interest rate which is further on dictated by the market forces. In other words, the loan price is flexible and can be adjusted according to the market conditions at any particular time.

However, this is not the case with BBA facility. Here, the price is fixed for the whole duration of the contract. It cannot be changed, even if the cost of the

¹⁰ Any increase according to majority of jurists of four schools of *fiqh* should contain *'iwad*, see (Rosly, 2005, p. 520).

underlying product has changed. The price of a product under BBA is set upfront at the beginning of the contract period. This price consists of the cost of that product bought by a bank and profit margin. The difference between the original price (i.e. market price) and selling price represents the legitimate profit the bank earns over the instalment period.

5.2.1 Rising Interest Rate and Inflation

Even though the BBA contract is 'interest-free', still we observe its vulnerability in case of rising and/or falling interest rate. This shows that BBA contracts are somehow linked, tied, and/or dependent on the movement of interest rate. Here we are going to see what happens when the interest rate goes up. Let us say that a central bank announces an increase in the interest rate or that the inflation takes place in the economy. Once this happens, the cost of funds will increase reciprocally. As result, the conventional banks will increase the interest rate on the loans and by doing so they will protect themselves from the adverse effect of rising interest rate and/or inflation.

When this happens, on the other hand, there is a great possibility that the customers will opt for the BBA facilities.¹¹ Because the price of BBA contracts cannot be changed, Islamic banks cannot do much about this increase in the interest rate and/or inflation. If they do change their selling price this would violate one of the principles of *al-bay'*. This principle states that the selling price cannot be changed. Now the loans are relatively more expensive than Islamic BBA financing facilities, so increase in demand for BBA facilities is understandable.

This increase in demand for BBA is something that is desirable. However, it is a difficult situation for Islamic banks, since they have locked their profit margins already. This means that Islamic banks lack necessary funds to increase BBA financing. Due to the increase in the interest rate, the rate on deposits also increases in case of conventional banks. Consequently, conventional deposits are more attractive to the customers than the Islamic deposits which yield relatively less return. To increase the rate of return on new deposits, for Islamic banks, is not a wise solution. This extra *hibah*, if given, would cut the profits of the Islamic banks, since they cannot generate revenue due to the locked-in BBA financing.

Finally, Islamic banks will face a serious problem. In order to generate more deposits they will have to borrow from inter-bank money market. However, the cost of these funds is higher than *hibah* given by Islamic banks.

From the above discussion, we can say that Islamic banks have two (2) options (Rosly, 2005, pp. 249-252) when the interest rate is rising, namely: (i) to increase *hibah* and dividend in order to remain competitive in the deposit market; or (ii) not to increase *hibah* and dividend rates.

We have to remember here that Islamic banks *cannot* change BBA profit rate. The question can be asked: Why Islamic bank cannot change the profit rate? The

¹¹ This is especially true when we are dealing with dual-banking system such as in Malaysia.

answer is relatively simple. Changing of the profit rate would bring uncertainty to the contract. This uncertainty makes a contract void. Therefore, if they go for the option (a) the profit will decline and the banking performance will be adversely affected. On the other side, if they go for the option (b) the profit will remain the same in the short-run. In addition, the customers would shift to conventional banks that offer higher interest rate on deposits. The deposits in Islamic banks will decrease and there will be an asset-liability mismatch.¹² In order to solve the problem Islamic banks will have to resort to the money market (an interest-based market) which is more expensive than bank deposits. At the end of the day, the profit of Islamic banks will fall. Islamic banks will lose, while non-Muslim, and even some Muslim, customers will gain. Here, we may ask one simple question: Having in mind the nature of Islamic banks and the prohibition of *ribā*, is it allowed for Islamic bank to resort to the money market for its financing needs?

In short, when the interest rate is rising, the following would be the result as stated by Rosly (2005, p. 251):

...non-Muslim customers will use BBA financing, but may place their savings in conventional deposits. By doing so, they have benefited in both worlds, namely, cheaper credit and higher returns on deposits. Muslim customers, on the other hand, don't have much choice but only to look. Islamic banks will be stuck with less deposit. To acquire funds at higher costs would cut down earnings.

The above citation indicates the process known as arbitrage. Here we see how the customers are performing arbitrage in order to gain from their investment (i.e. deposits).

5.2.2 Falling Interest Rate

When this happens, we could expect an increase in the borrowing by the household and business sector. The increase in borrowings will increase the consumption and investment. Finally, this will lead to the increase in the GDP. When this happens, Islamic banks will again face some serious problems. This decrease in the interest rate will lead to decline in demand for BBA financing, since BBA financing would be relatively more expensive option than conventional loans. Remember that BBA price and therefore, profit margin cannot be changed, while the interest rate on loans can be either increased or decreased.

On the other side, the fall in the interest rate will cause the interest rate on conventional deposits to go down. When this happens, the rate of return on Islamic deposit will be relatively higher than the interest rate on conventional deposits. As a

¹² When the asset-liability mismatch happens there are two scenarios. First scenario is when the deposits are greater than financing. This scenario will lead to the following: (i) excess liquidity; (ii) deposit expenses greater than revenues from financing; and (iii) lower profits. Second scenario is when the deposits are lower than financing. This will lead to the following: (i) higher cost of funds; (ii) deposit expenses greater than revenues from financing; and (iii) lower profits.

result we would see some of those conventional deposits being transferred to Islamic banks. A lower demand for BBA facilities combined with higher supply of Islamic deposits will lead to the excess liquidity. Islamic banks will be overburdened by deposits that they are unable to invest. Here again we see the convergence between the Islamic and conventional banks taking place.

Once again, non-Muslim customers are going to gain from the decline in the interest rate. When the interest rate falls, due to the lower cost of borrowing, they will use loans instead of BBA for financing purposes. At the same time, *hibah* paid by Islamic banks is relatively higher than the interest rate on deposit in conventional banks. This will increase the supply of Islamic deposits by non-Muslims.

In overall, as with the case of rising interest rate, here again Islamic banks have two (2) options when the interest rate is falling, namely: (i) to cut *hibah* and dividend in order to remain competitive in the deposit market; or (ii) to maintain *hibah* and dividend rates.

Cutting the *hibah* and dividend rates will increase the profit of Islamic banks. Islamic banks will gain, while its customers using BBA facilities will lose. They will still have to pay higher instalment and they will not be able to enjoy the decrease in the interest rate. In the short-run, the profit will remain the same if the option (b) is applied. BBA customers will lose again as stated above. In the long-run, Islamic banks may lose. If they keep the *hibah* at the initial level it will attract new deposits. Therefore, the supply of Islamic deposits will go up while there will be a big problem to use BBA for new contracts due to relatively higher cost. Again, we will see the asset-liability mismatch. Finally, the profit will decline.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on what we have said so far it can be concluded that BBA as a mode of finance, even though being allowed by *Shariah* scholars, is of a questionable validity because of the *modus operandi* or mechanism implemented in Malaysian Islamic banks. The extensive use of BBA contracts and overdependence of Islamic banks on debt-based modes of financing will result in convergence of Islamic bank into conventional, interest-based, banks. Therefore, its usage (the way it is practiced in Malaysian banks) as a mode of finance should be minimized as much as possible, if not eliminated from Islamic banks. By doing so, Islamic banks will move closer to the real objectives of *Shariah* (*maqāsid al- Shariah*).

The real BBA, as shown in Figure 2, is not taking place nowadays. There are currently no two contracts implemented when financing through BBA as it suggested by Chapra. For BBA to be a valid contract it should be carried out as presented in Figure 2. Unfortunately, presently BBA is taking place as shown in Figure 1. This is the fear that was mentioned by Chapra and many others and this is the problem we have to deal with as soon as possible.

It is believed Islamic banks need an innovative approach to the current situation. Without new instruments Islamic banks will face difficulties in sustaining their growth, development and coping with the increasing competition. The best way out of the above mentioned problems faced by BBA financing lies in the diversification of the financing products offered by Islamic banks.

Having said that, the Islamic banks have two options: (i) to use BBA in its true sense as presented in Figure 2 by becoming a more kind of traders rather than financial intermediaries; and/or (ii) to come up with new products that will make them more in line with *Shari'ah*. Therefore, we believe that the future researches should focus more on developing new instruments that will promote the true spirit of the Islamic financial system and make the financial instruments genuine and distinguishable from the conventional counterparts. Failing to make it distinguishable and genuine, the Islamic financial system is doomed to failure and with current practices it will lead to its convergence towards the conventional financial system. The sooner we realize our mistakes and make necessary corrections the sooner we will move forward and grow further, but until that is realized we will grow only within the dominant financial system, the conventional financial system.

Wallahu a'lamu!

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